

TOM BRADY AND THE VALUE OF A SAND GRAIN

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INTRODUCTION

On February 1, 2023, legendary quarterback Tom Brady announced his retirement through a self-recorded video on social media. Several opportunistic fans recognized the location as a beach in Surfside, Florida (Figures 1 and 2), and quickly collected sediment samples from the locale to sell on eBay. Though the original listing was removed by eBay after reaching a value of \$99,900, others managed to sell their jars of sand for various amounts up to \$15,000. These events provide an opportunity to examine the relative value of sand resources and ask some crucial and interesting questions about the local geology, such as: What were these collectors actually buying? How did it get there? And was this sand, temporarily shaded by Tom Brady's shadow, actually the most valuable sand in the world?

THE VALUE OF SAND

In the petroleum industry, the value of sand has historically been attached to its ability to provide subsurface sandstone reservoirs with relatively high porosity and permeability. However, in recent years it has become apparent that the sand grains themselves are a valuable natural resource. Sand is the most-extracted solid material in the world with an estimated 50 billion tons consumed yearly (UNEP, 2022). Sand is used in almost all major industries: the construction industry as an aggregate; the petroleum industry as a hydraulic fracturing proppant; the tech industry melts it down to make glass and silicon, and obviously the tourism industry in coastal environments relies heavily on sandy beach fronts such as the ones observed at Surfside, Florida (Figure 2).

Some governments, such as in Puerto Rico, have even reported sand theft (Rodriguez, 2017). Adding complication is the fact that this extensive sand extraction is unregulated. The United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP, 2022) has proposed more regulation, tracking of global sand usage, and incentives for finding sand alternatives in various projects. The extensive use of sand, combined with the effects of anthropogenic alteration of shorelines has limited sediment supply in many natural environments (Runyan and Griggs 2003; Anderson et al., 2014; Hackney et al., 2021). As a result, sand is more important and valuable than ever before. The average price of construction-grade sand has increased roughly 50% in the last 12 years (Figure 3). Though, even

with this increase, construction-grade sand can still cost as low as \$11 USD per metric ton, a price that continues to fuel heavy consumption.

Not all sand is valued the same, and a wide range exists. For example, construction quality sand sells for a relatively low price compared to \$10,000 USD/metric ton for specialized quartz sand used by the tech industry (Beiser, 2018). Indeed, that's a high price, but with price tags of \$15,000 to \$99,900 for a jar of sand, the Tom Brady retirement sand from Surfside is a strong candidate for the world's most valuable sand. With such a high cost, what would be the approximate price per sand grain? And what did people actually buy for that exorbitant price? Let's break this down, first by price per sand grain.

To calculate the price per grain of sand, we must first estimate how many grains of sand fit inside that mason jar. There are many ways of doing this calculation, but we will use the following methodology: The jar in the image appears to be a 16 oz mason jar, or approximately 473 mL of volume. At this point, several assumptions are needed to proceed: 1) We will assume the grains are packed in a hexagonal close packing configuration, yielding about 40% porosity. 2) We assume all the sand grains are medium-grained. 3) We assume all the sand grains approximate a spherical shape with radius of 0.165 mm.

FIGURE 1:

A) Image from Tom Brady's social media post announcing his retirement (via TomBrady/IG). In this image, and throughout the video, sand can be seen under him (white arrow), suggesting he is at the edge of the vegetation at the eastern edge of the beach. The buildings in the background can be used as a reference for his location.

B) Image from the eBay listing for the jar of sand that generated bids of \$90,900 (via SportsCenter/IG). Red arrows indicate common buildings between the images to assist with the location verification.

FIGURE 2: Geologic map of southern Florida (modified from Neal et al., 2008). Inset map to the right shows the location of the video recording and where the sand was collected (white pinpoint). The coordinates of this point are 25.8835471, -80.1206069. The image also shows the barrier island, as well as flood and ebb tidal deltas (blue and white arrows respectively) on either side of the artificially created Haulover Inlet. The green dashed box shows the location featured in Figure 5.

The volume of a sphere can be calculated with the following formula:

$$V = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3$$

With a radius of 0.165 mm, the volume of each sand grain becomes 0.0192 mm³. The jar's volume of 473 mL then converts to 4.73×10⁵ mm³. Using these components, along with the assumed porosity of 40%, the estimated number of sand grains in this jar is:

$$(4.73 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^3 (\text{volume of jar})) / ((0.0192 \text{ mm}^3 \text{ grain}) \times (1 - 0.4)) = 14,781,250 \text{ sand grains.}$$

At \$99,900 for the entire jar, the price works out to \$0.0068 USD per grain. With the value of this sand established, let's address the second question: "What were these people actually bidding on?"

THE SAND OF SOUTH FLORIDA

Surfside is located on a barrier island extending off the southeastern portion of the Florida peninsula. The location is just south of an inlet with visible flood and ebb tidal deltas (Figure 2). Predominantly, this is a carbonate system overtopped with coral and shell fragments from the ocean, as well as inland erosion and sediment transport to the coast contributing to the overall sediment load. Sand migrates north-to-south,

meaning the health of the barrier island system depends upon the constant delivery of sand from the north. Visible on satellite imagery, a series of jetties and seawalls along the shoreline limit sediment delivery to this barrier island. There are five inlets with artificial seawalls within 75 km to the north of the Tom Brady retirement location. The satellite imagery shows that these structures are trapping sand and preventing its natural migration, as apparent by sand-starved beaches to the south of the structures (Figure 4).

Perhaps the best place to visualize the importance of sand is at the Kennedy Space Center at Cape Canaveral, FL, where the sand on the beach protects NASA's access to space (Figure 5). Cape Canaveral relies on constant sand delivery via alongshore migration from the north. Historical satellite images show sediment migrating around the tip of the cape, being deposited on the shoreline to the south. This results in net erosion north of the cape, and net deposition along the south (Adams, 2018; Mackenzie et al., 2023).

If sediment delivery were to be diminished, erosion on the north side of the cape would accelerate significantly. The same sediment budget dynamics exists in other locations along the Florida coastline, although less visible than Cape Canaveral. As such, the barriers to sediment migration in South Florida, combined with continued sea-level rise can be devastating to these shallow marine environments. This has prompted extensive beach renourishment projects to protect local beaches and maintain their appeal as tourist destinations.

Beach sand in South Florida was already valuable, as local governments invest millions of dollars keeping their beaches looking pristine. In 2019, Miami-Dade County reported that it had funding of \$158.3M USD for this beach renourishment project (refer to the Miami-Dade County, Surfside Beach Renourishment Project report). While this is an expensive

FIGURE 3: Average price of construction-grade sand and gravel in the US from 2010 to 2022 (statista.com).

FIGURE 4: Contrast between beaches on the proximal side (white arrows) of jetties vs the distal side (yellow arrows) where beaches are artificially starved of sediment migrating south along the beach. Location A) 26.093958, -80.104335, approximately 24 km to the north of the Tom Brady retirement location. Location B) 26.3363573, -80.0722546, approximately 50 km to the north of the Tom Brady retirement location.

project, it pales in comparison to the potential loss of tourism dollars, as Miami-Dade County collects around \$10-20 USD billion per year in revenue from tourism. Pristine beaches are a major component of the region's tourist attractions.

Anthropogenic barriers to sediment migration have left this beach in Surfside starved for sediment and prone to damage from storms and continued sea-level rise. To combat these effects, local governments have undertaken beach alimentation efforts designed to replace the sediment that is continuously removed by natural sedimentary processes. These usually involve dredging sand from nearshore environments and placing it back on the beach, where tractors spread it out and let nature resume its natural processes (Figure 6). If this is not performed, the beach would continue to erode and eventually threaten the town. As a result, the "Tom Brady sand" was not deposited there by natural sources, but rather by a fleet of heavy machinery contracted by local governments to maintain tourism (Figure 6 inset).

The methods of sand nourishment in South Florida are relatively inefficient. Sand is dredged offshore, trucked onto the beach with large dump trucks, and re-distributed with bulldozers. From there, the natural process of wave energy reworks, transports, and ultimately removes the sand. In an effort to preserve a natural environment as much as possible, local governments (including that of Surfside) have established specifications for nourished sand. All sand must meet the following specifications (as per the Miami-Dade County, Surfside Beach Renourishment Project report):

- Sand must be predominantly CaCO_3 or quartz, with no more than 5% comprising other minerals.
- Average grain size between 0.30 mm and 0.55 mm, with standard deviation between 0.50 phi and 1.75 phi (poorly sorted to moderately well sorted).
- Silt and clay content less than 5% of total volume.
- 95% of the sand must pass through the 4.76 mm sieve, 99% must pass through the 9.51 mm sieve, and 100% must pass through the 19.0 mm sieve.
- Sand must be naturally created. Crushed rock constitutes manufactured sand and is prohibited.
- Sand color must resemble that of the existing beach.

These requirements provide a detailed description of the contents of the Tom Brady sand. In addition to providing the information on composition, they have also provided information on the cost of obtaining sand that meets this description. In 2019 this sand had costs ranging from \$50 to \$65 per cubic yard. To convert the price per cubic yard to metric tonnes, we use the following calculation:

Each cubic yard is equivalent to 764,555 cm^3 . Given a sand density of 1.52 gm/cm^3 , we multiply them together to get a weight of 1162.12 kg, which we divide by 1000 to get 1.162 metric tonnes for each cubic yard. Using the higher end of the price spectrum for the Miami beach sand, we get \$65/1.162 tons, which works out to a price of approximately \$56/metric ton. This is significantly higher than the \$11 per metric ton of sand used in construction projects, which makes sense given its specific requirements. How does this compare to the price of the Tom Brady sand? The jar of sand seen on eBay appears to have been a 16 oz mason jar. One cubic yard contains 25,852.7 fluid ounces, or 4,308.8 16 oz mason jars. If each jar is worth \$99,900, then one cubic yard works out to \$430,449,120, which works out to \$370,438,141 per metric ton of sand. We can then conclude that Tom Brady's temporary presence multiplied the value of this artificially placed sand by over 6.5 million times!

CONCLUSION

The exorbitant sums of money paid for artificially emplaced sand, which skyrocketed in value when it temporarily contacted the backside of Tom Brady, has allowed us to examine the current state of sand resources around the world. In what is likely the most valuable sand in the world, we have calculated the "Tom Brady sand" to be worth approximately \$0.0068 USD per grain, or \$370,438,141 per metric ton, compared to \$11 per ton in construction projects. However, it is this relatively cheap price for sand (that has not been graced by a superstar) that continues to fuel the excessive consumption of this increasingly scarce resource. Repercussions of this impending sand shortage will be increasingly problematic for a variety of industries and locations, including the very spot that generated the sand on which Tom Brady sat for his latest retirement announcement.

FIGURE 5 (ABOVE): Aerial photography from 1943 of Cape Canaveral showing that Launch Complex LC-39A was built on sand deposited by a flood tide delta. It also shows the proximity of the shoreline, and how erosion of the shoreline could impact the launch infrastructure (Modified from Mackenzie et al. 2023).

FIGURE 6 (BELOW): Time slices of the Tom Brady retirement location (red pinpoint). Initially this beach was approximately 25-m wide. In December of 2019, beach nourishment construction can be seen at the south side of the image (panels B and C). By February of 2020, the widening of the beach had progressed to the north of the Tom Brady retirement location (see panel D, green arrow). By March of 2020 (panel E), the beach is more than double the width seen in panel A.

As sea-level continues to rise, and human development continues to hinder sediment delivery to the coast, beaches like those found in Surfside, Florida, will have to develop solutions to address their sand supply issues. Is perpetual sand nourishment sustainable in the long-term? Are seawalls, jetties, and other inhibitors to sediment movement worth the damaging effects they have on coastlines? Are there more sustainable solutions to protecting coastlines? These are important issues in which

geologists will have a tremendously important role. Geologists will be crucial for helping resolve sediment budgets and evaluating sediment migration pathways in these sensitive depositional environments. In addition, geologists can help identify sustainable replacements for limited sand resources around the world. And hopefully, Tom Brady's next retirement announcement will feature another geologically interesting location.

REFERENCES

- Adams, P.N. (2018). Geomorphic origin of Merritt Island-Cape Canaveral, Florida, USA: A paleodelta of the reversed St. Johns River? *Geomorphology*, v. 306. p. 102-107.
- Anderson, J. B., Wallace, D. J., Simms, A. R., Rodriguez, A. B., & Milliken, K. T. (2014). Variable response of coastal environments of the northwestern Gulf of Mexico to sea-level rise and climate change: Implications for future change. *Marine Geology*, 352, 348-366.
- Beiser, V. (2018). The Ultra-Pure, Super-Secret Sand That Makes Your Phone Possible. *Wired Magazine*. <https://www.wired.com/story/book-excerpt-science-of-ultra-pure-silicon/>
- Hackney, C. R., Vasilopoulos, G., Heng, S., Darbari, V., Walker, S., & Parsons, D. R. (2021). Sand mining far outpaces natural supply in a large alluvial river. *Earth Surface Dynamics*, 9(5), 1323-1334.
- Mackenzie, R., Bremner, P., Laycock, D., Fletcher, S., Pemberton, E. (2023). Visualizing Sedimentological Variability Near Vulnerable NASA Infrastructure at Cape Canaveral, FL and Wallops Island, VA. *Geoconvention 2023*.
- Neal, A., Grasmueck, M., McNeill, D. F., Viggiano, D. A., & Eberli, G. P. (2008). Full-resolution 3D radar stratigraphy of complex oolitic sedimentary architecture: Miami Limestone, Florida, USA. *Journal of Sedimentary Research*, 78(9), 638-653.
- Rodriguez, R.W. (2017). Sand and Gravel Resources of Puerto Rico. USGS Fact Sheet. <https://pubs.usgs.gov/fs/sand-gravel/>
- Runyan, K., & Griggs, G. B. (2003). The effects of armoring seacliffs on the natural sand supply to the beaches of California. *Journal of coastal research*, 336-347.
- UNEP. (2022). Sand and sustainability: 10 strategic recommendations to avert a crisis. GRID-Geneva, United Nations Environment Programme, Geneva, Switzerland; URL : <https://unepgrid.ch/en/resource/2022SAND>
- Miami-Dade County, Surfside Beach Renourishment Project report (2019). https://townofsurfsidefl.gov/docs/default-source/newsletters/miami-dade-county-beach-renourishment-project.pdf?sfvrsn=8cb45c94_4